

REVIEW ON EPIDEMIOLOGY AND PUBLIC HEALTH SIGNIFICANCE OF BOVINE LISTERIOSIS

TESHALE ADERE SENBENTA

JIMMA UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND VETERINARY MEDICINE SCHOOL OF VETERINARY MEDICINE

Abstract:

Listeriosis is a bacterial zoonotic food born disease caused by different *Listeria* species; among them *Listeria monocytogenes* (*L. monocytogenes*) being the most pathogenic species of ruminant animals and humans. This paper aimed to describe the current epidemiological aspects of Listeriosis and briefly point out public health importance of Bovine Listeriosis. A wide variety of animal species can be infected by *L. monocytogenes*, including mammals, birds, fish, and crustaceans. The disease is characterized by septicemia, encephalitis, meningitis, meningoenzephalitis, rhombencephalitis, abortion, stillbirth, perinatal infections and gastroenteritis. The organism is truly ubiquitous in the environment where as a source infection commonly isolated from animal feces, human feces, farm slurry, sewerage sludge, soil, farm water troughs, surface water, plants, animal and the walls, floors, and drains of farms and other environments. The organism is truly ubiquitous in the environment and can be commonly isolated from animal feces, human feces, farm slurry, sewerage sludge, soil, farm water troughs, surface water, plants, animal and the walls, floors, and drains of farms and other environments. Transmission of *L. monocytogenes* is principally via fecal-oral route through the consumption of contaminated food, raw or contaminated milk, vegetables, and ready-to eat meat have been the cause of worldwide outbreaks. Animals are exposed by ingestion, inhalation, or direct contact with the *Listeria* bacterium. Listeriosis causes encephalitis, abortion, mastitis, repeat breeding and endometriosis in animals. Diagnosis of the disease by molecular methods are accurate, sensitive and specific, they are increasingly used in identification of *L. monocytogenes* from foods. The optimal antibiotic treatment for Listeriosis was penicillin, ampicillin, erythromycin rifampicin, chloramphenicol, tetracycline, and aminoglycosides, with the exception of cephalosporin are effective against *L. monocytogenes*. Control of the disease is difficult because of the ubiquitous occurrence of the organism and a poor understanding of the risk factors. However, as Listeriosis is one of the important food-borne bacterial zoonotic diseases worldwide and due to the increasing incidence, the public health learning through Mass-media, radio and teaching livestock holder's and people who are at risk to *Listeria monocytogenes* is important besides, Consumption of unpasteurized milk and milk products should be avoided.

Keywords: Epidemiology, Bovine, Listeriosis, Food born pathogen, Public health significance.

✓ Introduction:

Listeriosis is a bacterial zoonotic food born disease caused by different *Listeria* species; among them *Listeria monocytogenes* (*L. monocytogenes*) being the most pathogenic species of ruminant animals and humans (CDC, 2008). There are 7 species of *Listeria* *L. monocytogenes*, *L. innocua*, *L. welshimeri*, *L. seeligeri*, *L. ivanovii*, *L. murrayi*, and *L. grayi*. *L. monocytogenes* is the only species of *Listeria* that is pathogenic for both humans and animals (Chakraborty and Hain, 2003). *Listeria* is Gram-positive rods, nonspore-forming and facultative anaerobe bacterium. *Listeria monocytogenes* adapts well in stressful environmental conditions, it is able to overcome different degrees of acidity, osmolarity and oxygen differences (WHO, 2005). The organism is truly ubiquitous in the environment and can be commonly isolated from animal feces, human feces, farm slurry, sewerage sludge, soil, farm water troughs, surface water, plants, animal and the walls, floors, and drains of farms and other environments (CFSPH, 2005). Transmission of *L. monocytogenes* is principally via fecal-oral route through the consumption of contaminated food, raw or contaminated milk, vegetables, and ready-to eat meat have been the cause of worldwide outbreaks (Heymann, 2004). Animals are exposed by ingestion, inhalation, or direct contact with the *Listeria* bacterium (Ramaswamy et al., 2007).

Over the last few decades, *Listeria monocytogenes* has been responsible for foodborne diseases. It is considered a causative agent of Listeriosis and one of the leading foodborne pathogens and has been implicated in numerous outbreaks. It was recognized as a foodborne human pathogen in 1981. For healthy people, the ingestion of highly contaminated food causes

gastroenteritis, while for elderly individuals, pregnant women, children/newborns, and immunocompromised patients, even low levels of food contamination could be cause in septicemia and encephalitis, infection of the fetus resulting in abortion or stillbirth(WHO,2005;L.Radoshevich and P.Cossart,2018; Luque-Sastre et al.,2018).Listeriosis, also termed as silage disease, circling disease and meningoencephalitis, is caused by *Listeria monocytogenes*. It is an infectious and fatal disease of animals, birds, fish, crustaceans and humans where septicemia and encephalitis are predominantly observed (OIE, 2014). Throughout the world, Listeriosis occurs in a sporadic or epidemic form (, Malik, et al., 2008). Most of the time, infection in animals is subclinical but severe forms can also occur (OIE, 2014). The disease is characterized by septicemia, encephalitis, meningitis, meningoencephalitis, rhombencephalitis, abortion, stillbirth, perinatal infections and gastroenteritis (Limmahakun & Chayakulkeeree, 2013; OIE,2014). The organism has an intracellular life cycle that can pass from cell to cell without release from the cell. This ability presents its potential to cross placental barrier and bloodbrain barrier, explaining its pathogenesis and clinical signs. The organism can survive at varying temperatures ranging from 4 to 37 C (Janakiraman, 2008). Due to poor measures of quality control during food processing/handling and packaging, contamination of *L. monocytogenes* may occur (Charpentier & Cerf ,2011), raising concerns for public health (Dhama, Rajagunalan, et al. ,2013).

The diseases can be tentatively diagnosed based on history, clinical signs and epidemiological findings and Post mortem findings (Tewodros, and Atsedewoyne, 2012). As molecular methods are accurate, sensitive and specific, they are increasingly used in Identification of *L. monocytogenes* from foods. Various molecular methods used are DNA hybridization, polymerase chain reaction and real time PCR (RT PCR) (Hough et al, 2002). Listeriosis is treated with antibiotics; depending on the form of the disease, treatment may take up to six weeks or more. Due to some bacteria's intracellular location and disease occurrence in debilitated patients, the cure rate can be low (CDC, 2005). Control is difficult because of the ubiquitous occurrence of the organism, the lack of a simple method of determining when it is present in high numbers in the environment and a poor understanding of the risk factors other than silage (Radostits et al.,2006). Timely detection, keeping away/eliminating possible sources of infection, maintaining high hygiene/sanitation standards are crucial factors for disease prevention (Dhama et al.,2015). As, listeriosis is one of the major emerging food borne diseases in the world and zoonotic infectious disease of humans and animals. Therefore, the objectives of this seminar paper are:

- ✓ To describe the current epidemiological aspects of Listeriosis and
- ✓ To briefly point out public health importance of Bovine Listeriosis

✓ LITRATURE REVIEW:

2.1 Etiology

Listeriosis is a serious illness caused by eating food contaminated with the bacterium *Listeria*, which is a Gram-positive psychotropic, facultatively anaerobic, none sporulating, motile, small rod and it displays characteristic tumbling motility that is facilitated by the presence of peritrichous flagella. Motility is temperature-dependent, showing high motility at 20-30°C when the flagellar expression is maximum. There are 7 species of *Listeria* *L. monocytogenes*, *L. innocuous*, *L. welshimeri*, *L. seeligeri*, *L. Ivanovic*, *L. murrayi*, and *L. grayi*. *L. monocytogenes* is the only species of listeria that is pathogenic for both humans and animals (Chakraborty and Hain, 2003). The Genus *Listeria* contains seven species but one is most pathogenic for both animal and human beings. The most important species is *L. monocytogenes* a gram-positive facultatively anaerobic bacillus 0.5 to 2 microns long and 0.5 microns in diameter that is motile at temperatures between 20°C and 25°C also it is beta-hemolytic in blood agar and forms a narrow band of hemolysis around the colonies (unlike *L. Ivanovic*, which forms a wide band). A noteworthy characteristic of *L. monocytogenes* is its ability to grow at low temperatures; at a pH between 6 and 9, Painste and Slutsker).

Listeriosis is caused by members of the genus *Listeria*, a Gram-positive bacterial rod in the family *Listeriaceae*. *L. monocytogenes* is the primary pathogen in humans and animals, but *L. ivanovii* is found occasionally, and there are rare reports of clinical cases caused by *L. seeligeri*, *L. grayi* (which includes the former *L. murrayi*), and *L. innocuous*. *Listeria* is a Gram-positive pathogen with the ability to adapt to a wide range of conditions such as refrigeration temperatures (2–4 °C) and acidic and high-salt conditions. *Listeria* cells are slow growers and may be rapidly outgrown by competitors (Kelly, 2015).

2.2. Morphology and Growth Characteristics of Listeria:

Listeria species are small, Gram-positive, non- acid-fast non-spore forming and non-capsulate coccobacilli measuring 0.5 to 2 mm x 0.4 to 0.5 mm. *Listeria* has typical Gram-positive cell wall. They are facultative anaerobes that grow best under reduced oxygen and increased carbon dioxide concentration. Growth occurs at 4 to 45°C, with an optimum temperature of 30 to 37°C. Simple laboratory media support growth preferably at an alkaline or neutral PH. *Listeria* tolerates 0.04% potassium tellurite,

0.025% thallium acetate, 3.75% potassium thiocyanate, 10% NaCl and 40% bile in media. Most strains grow over pH range of 5.5 to 9.6. It has greater heat tolerance than other non-spore forming bacteria; however, short-time other non-spore forming bacteria; however, short-time high temperature pasteurization is effective for killing high listeria (Tewodros, and Atsedewoyne, 2012).

2.2. Epidemiology:

2.2.1. Geographical distribution

Although the organism is widespread in nature, clinical diseases in animals occur mainly in the northern and southern latitudes. They are much less common in tropical and subtropical than in temperate (WHO,2019). For example, the Listeriosis outbreak in South Africa remains the largest in the world with over 1000 laboratory-confirmed cases and over 200 fatalities (Dufailu et al.,2021). The disease is important in North America, Europe, United Kingdom New Zealand and Australia (Radotists, 2007). Seasonally in the northern hemisphere, Listeriosis has a distinct seasonal occurrence, probably associated with seasonal feeding of silage, with the highest prevalence in the months of December but seasonal occurrence is not a features of Australia (Quinn et al.,2002).regarding the host Listeriosis is primarily a disease of ruminants and the major disease associated with *L. monocytogenes* are encephalitis and abortion; rarely producing syndromes of septicemia, spinal myelitis, uveitis, gastroenteritis and mastitis (Andrews et al.,2004).

2.2.2. Host range

A wide variety of animal species can be infected by *L. monocytogenes*, including mammals, birds, fish, and crustaceans. Although most clinical Listeriosis cases occur in ruminants, pigs rarely develop disease, and birds. Most animal infections are subclinical, but the invasive disease can occur sporadically or as an outbreak. In addition to the economic impact of Listeriosis in ruminants and other animal species, ruminants may be a source of infection for humans, primarily from consuming contaminated animal products (WOAH, 2000).

2.2.3. Source of infection and mode of transmission

The organism is truly ubiquitous in the environment and can be commonly isolated from animal feces, human feces, farm slurry, sewerage sludge, soil, farm water troughs, surface water, plants, animal and the walls, floors, and drains of farms and other environments (CFSPH, 2005). The capacity to form biofilm may assist its survival in the feed and environment and maintain its life in water troughs on infected farms. Most feed hays, grains, and formulated feeds have the potential to contain *L. monocytogenes*, but the scarcity of water restricts its multiplication (Quinn and Markey, 2003).

Transmission of *L. monocytogenes* is principally via fecal-oral route through the consumption of contaminated food, raw or contaminated milk, vegetables, and ready-to eat meat have been the cause of worldwide outbreaks (Heymann, 2004). Animals are exposed by ingestion, inhalation, or direct contact with the *Listeria* bacterium. The organism has been found in water, birds, urine, aborted fetuses, uterine discharge and milk. Food-borne transmission is the most common mode of transmission and *Listeria* is considered a food-borne pathogen for large ruminant. In large ruminant, *Listeria* is most frequently transmitted by contaminated silage. It is most often found in silage that is poorly fermented with a PH =5.6, in moldy silage, or in silage spoiled with soil (Ramaswamy et al., 2007).

2.4. Risk Factors:

2.4.1. Host risk factors

Host susceptibility plays a major role in clinical disease presentation upon exposure to *L. monocytogenes*. Thus, most Listeriosis patients have a physiological or pathological defect that affects T-cell-mediated immunity (Figure 1). This justifies the classification of *L.monocytogenes* as an opportunistic pathogen (Longhi et al.,2004).The groups at risk for Listeriosis are pregnant women and neonates, the elderly (55 to 60 years and older), and immunocompromised or debilitated adults with underlying diseases (Roberts and Wiedmann,2022).Listeriosis in nonpregnant adults is associated in most cases (75%) with at least one of the following conditions: malignancies (leukemia, lymphoma, or sarcoma) and liver disease (cirrhosis or alcoholism), kidney disease, diabetes, and collagen disease lupus (Kundul and Ame, 2022). Other groups of individuals at increased risk include those on drugs that reduce gastric acidity, patients with cirrhosis, and chronic renal failure (Longhi et al., 2004). Genetic variation between human hosts, as well as the presence or absence of certain behavioral risk factors, may result in differences in susceptibility to infection by pathogenic *Listeria* and to different disease outcomes (Rad et al., 2002).

2.4.2. Pathogen risk factor

Several pathogen-specific factors influence the outcome of human and animal infection with a pathogenic *Listeria* strain. These

can be grouped into the general categories of virulence genes (or those genes that are essential for pathogenesis) and virulence-related genes, or those genes that are not essential for pathogenesis but can enhance it (Bandelet et al., 2018). A virulence gene can be broadly defined according to molecular Koch's postulates. These postulates require true virulence genes to fulfill the following criteria. First, the gene must be present in pathogenic strains and absent (or at least mutated or not expressed) in nonpathogenic strains; second, disrupting the gene should reduce its virulence and third, the gene should be expressed when the pathogen is in the host environment (Longhi et al., 2004). Virulence-related genes, in contrast, might be common to both pathogenic and nonpathogenic strains, redundant in function and expressed outside a host, but still assist the infectious process (Figure 1) (Rad et al., 2002).

2.4.3. Management and environmental risk factors

The evidence indicates that animal Listeriosis is frequently associated with stored forage and the environment as the main source of contamination. In the environment, this saprophytic microorganism can live in soil, water, and decaying vegetables, from which it could contaminate animal feed. Silage is the most frequent source (Longhi et al., 2004). Several factors in food or natural environments play an important role in the survival and growth of pathogenic Listeria, including, but not limited to, temperature, water availability, and pH (Figure 1). Listeria monocytogenes can grow over a wide range of temperatures (1-45°C) and survive water activities as low as 0.83% (Roberts and Wiedemann, 2022). Such flexibility in temperature and water requirements might contribute to the abundance of Listeria in the environment. From a human health perspective, L. monocytogenes can survive and grow at refrigeration temperature (4°C) and at low water activities inhibiting many other food-borne pathogens (Quinn et al., 2011). For instance, 78 strains of L. monocytogenes were tested for their ability to grow on tryptone soy agar at sub-refrigeration temperatures. They determined that their mean minimum growth temperature was 1.1 (±0.3) °C (Longhi et al., 2004). Similarly, it was demonstrated extended survival of L. monocytogenes in low water activity foods such as hard salami and cheddar cheese (Pron et al., 2001).

Figure 1. Schematic presentation of determinants in listeriosis disease

Source: (Rad et al., 2002).

2.5. Pathogenesis:

Exposure to Listeria occurs via oral route. Entry into intestinal epithelial cells or M cells is mediated by internalin, a surface protein and its interaction with host cell receptors. After passage through the intestinal barrier, Listeria can be observed in phagocytic cells within the lamina propria. Further dissemination occurs via the blood stream. Listeria can be internalized by phagocytic cells or non-phagocytic cells through induced phagocytosis. After internalization, it escapes from phagosome, becomes associated with actin filaments in the cytoplasm and propels itself to the cell's plasma membrane protrusions and thus avoids host defense mechanism (Ramaswamy et al., 2007). An alternative proposed route of entry has been through damaged mucosal surfaces, inhalation, or by conjunctival contamination. It then invades the CNS by travelling along the trigeminal nerve sheath. This route of infection usually results in meningoencephalitis. However, there has been no evidence for tropism of the organism to neural tissue and it is unknown whether the organism can use nerves other than the trigeminal nerve to access the brain. The incubation period of L. monocytogenes infection is usually 2-6 weeks (Burgess and Lohmann, 2006).

2.6 Clinical Signs:

2.6.1. Clinical signs in animals

Clinical outcome depends on the number of organisms ingested, pathogenic properties of the strains of Listeria and the immune

status of the host. Three different forms of Listeriosis are documented in animals, namely septicemic, encephalitic and abortion form. Listeriosis causes encephalitis, abortion, mastitis, repeat breeding and endometriosis in animals (Malik et al., 2002). It is primarily a disease of ruminants, particularly sheep, and causes encephalitis and abortion. In ruminants, it also

produces syndromes of septicemia, spinal myelitis, uveitis, gastroenteritis and mastitis (Rawool et al., 2007; Headley et al., 2014). The encephalitic form is known as 'circling disease' due to movement of the animal in circles in one direction (OIE, 2014). Occasionally, septicemic disease occurs in horses and pigs. Outbreaks of Listeriosis are uncommon in birds and disease is observed occasionally in young chicks. The disease is sporadic/rare in poultry, usually seen as a septicemia or localized encephalitis. Besides causing disease in domestic animals and birds, *L. monocytogenes* also affects rodents and wild animal population (OIE, 2014).

Sheep can be severely affected by Listeriosis and the signs include encephalitis (i.e. circling disease) with brainstem and cranial nerve dysfunction, abortion with placentas in the last trimester (from 12 weeks on) and gastroenteritis with septicemia (Rawool et al., 2007; OIE, 2014). Young lambs (under 5 weeks of age) might develop the septicemic form while the encephalitic form is noticed in older lambs (4-8 months). Signs vary between individual sheep; however, incoordination, head deviation sometimes with tilting of head, walking in circles, propelling themselves forward till getting a solid object like wall or gate and unilateral facial paralysis (causing drooling of saliva, drooping of eyelid and ear) are observed (Scott 2013). Death occurs in 2-3 days due to respiratory failure. Goats and cattle exhibit similar signs like sheep (OIE, 2014). However, in cattle; the disease course is long and takes about 1-2 weeks. Buffaloes are also susceptible to Listeriosis where genital tract infections are common (Shakuntala et al., 2006). The cerebral form of Listeriosis also occurs in camels (Al-Swailem et al., 2010).

Bovine listeriosis is an acute bacterial infection of the central nervous system, which causes circling disease in addition to abortions in pregnant cattle. The disease is caused by a bacterium named *L. monocytogenes*, found in the brain stem or uterus of affected cattle. The organism enters the body of animals either orally or intranasally and then move to the bloodstream via the lymphatics. It is then carried to the brain stem, where the infection localizes and accounts for the clinical signs (Kundul and Ame, 2022). Listeriosis patients are neurologically very similar to Thrombo-embolic Meningo-encephalitis (TEM) patients, especially with unilateral or asymmetrical bilateral cranial nerve involvement. Compared to animals affected by TEM, animals suffering from listeriosis are much more ambulatory than and not as helpless as TEM animals. Listeriosis victims separate themselves from the herd and wander aimlessly or in circles (CFSPH, 2005). Drooling saliva is a constant sign with secondary corneal opacity following the loss of seventh nerve function (Vallejo et al., 2010-2020).

2.6.2. Clinical signs in humans

Listeriosis is usually a serious problem only in pregnant women, newborns, elderly, and immunocompromised or debilitated hosts. Pregnant women may experience either a mild, flu-like syndrome with fever, chills, headache, slight dizziness or gastrointestinal signs, or asymptomatic infection (Gaskell et al., 2017). This may be followed in a few days to weeks by abortion, stillbirth, premature birth or septicemia in the newborn. Abortions usually occur during the second half of pregnancy and are most frequent in the third trimester (Barisani-Asenbauer et al., 2012). Newborns may be infected either in utero or from bacteria found in the vagina during delivery. These infants can develop septicemia, disseminated granulomatosis; respiratory disease or meningitis (Kenyan et al., 2012). Symptoms may be present at birth or develop within a few days to several weeks. The clinical signs of a central nervous system (CNS) infection may include confusion, seizures, cranial nerve deficits, ataxia, tremors, or myoclonus (CFSPH, 2005).

2.7. Diagnosis:

The diseases can be tentatively diagnosed based on history, clinical signs and epidemiological findings and Post mortem findings (Tewodros and Atsedewoyne, 2012).

2.7.1. Direct microscope

A direct smear of infected tissue may reveal numerous gram-positive rods in septicemia and abortions; however, only few numbers of organisms are observed in encephalitic form (Largent et al., 2000). Histological examination of fixed 10% formalin brain tissue can often there are no distinct gross give a presumptive diagnosis of neural Listeriosis (Radostits, et al., 2007).

2.7 .2. Culture and isolation

Appropriate specimens include CSF, blood and amniotic fluid. *Listeria* is facultatively anaerobic and readily grows on routine laboratory media such as BAP chocolate and CNA agars. Its small, gray colonies are surrounded by a narrow zone of α -hemolysis. At times it may be necessary to remove a colony in order to observe the hemolysis (Bartle, 2000). Sample are plated on sheep blood agar and incubated at 35°C in 10% CO₂. Isolation of *L. monocytogenes* from brain tissue may be enhanced by pour plate methods. After the initial isolation attempts, remaining tissue is stored at 4°C for "cold enrichment" Such tissue is sub cultured weekly for up to 12 weeks. Cold enrichment is not necessary for isolation from listerial abortions or septicemias (OIE, 2008). For samples where contamination is likely, enrichment and the use of selective media (lithium chloride phenylethane-moxalactam

2.7.3. Identification

This small, gram positive, non-spore forming rod may appear coccobacillary or coccoid. *Listeria monocytogenes* is catalase and bile-esculin positive. Motility tests are important in *Listeria* identification (OIE, 2008). Broth motility; two broth tubes are inoculated with the test organism and incubated for several hours. One tube is incubated at 35°C and another is held at room temperature (25°C). When examined microscopically in a wet mount preparation, *L. monocytogenes* exhibits tumbling, end-over-end (“head-over-heads”) motility at 25°C and little motility at 35°C. Whereas semisolid agar motility; this test is performed by stabbing the test organisms once in to a tube of semisolid agar and then incubating the tube overnight at 25°C. *L. monocytogenes* produces an umbrella-like growth (Bartle, 2000).

2.7.4. Animal inoculation

Most isolates of animal origin are virulent, a characteristic which can be confirmed by animal inoculation. Anton Test is performed by inoculating a drop of broth culture into conjunctiva of rabbit or guinea pig. Only *L. monocytogenes* causes purulent keratoconjunctivitis within 24 - 36 hours of inoculation. Both *L. monocytogenes* and *L. ivanovii* are pathogenic for mice. Intraperitoneal inoculation of mice with a 24-hour broth culture results of their death within 5 days with necrotic lesions in the liver (Tewodros and Atsedewoyne, 2012).

2.7.5. Molecular methods

As molecular methods are accurate, sensitive and specific, they are increasingly used in Identification of *L. monocytogenes* from foods. Various molecular methods used are DNA hybridization, polymerase chain reaction and real time PCR (RT PCR). Among these, PCR and real time PCR are now established methods for identification of *Listeria monocytogenes* from other non-virulent *Listeria* spp. from foods. The real-time PCR is a very sensitive and quantitative method for detection of pathogen and thus has emerged as most important tool for *L. monocytogenes* detection and quantitation in foods (Hough et al, 2002).

2.7.6. Post mortem findings

Typically, there are no distinct gross changes associated with *Listeria* encephalitis. Histological examination of CNS tissue is necessary to demonstrate the micro-abscesses that are characteristics of the disease. Those are present in the brain stem in listerial encephalitis and in the cervical and/or lumbar spinal cord in outbreak of spin myelitis. Gram staining of paraffin-embedded tissue may permit confirmation of the diagnosis in cases for which suitable culture material is unavailable (Radostits et al., 2007). Visceral (septicemic) lesions occur as multiple foci of necrosis in the liver, spleen and myocardium in the septicemic form and in aborted fetus, aborted fetus is usually edematous and autolyzed, with very large number of bacteria visible microscopically in a variety of tissues (Quinn et al., 2002).

2.8. Differential diagnosis

The differential diagnosis of listeriosis is commonly related to diseases affecting nerve system, such as sexual excitement, vocalization, vigorous wool pulling, aggressiveness, hyperexcitability, hyperesthesia, which can be considered as a clinic sign (Kundul and Ame, 2022).

Gad (Coenurus or Sturdy) is a disease caused by invasion of the brain and spinal cord by the intermediate stage of *Taenia multiceps*. Blindness, deviation of the head with circling in the direction of the blind eye occurs. At necropsy, thin-walled cysts may be present anywhere in the brain, but most commonly found on the external surface of the cerebral hemisphere (Radostits et al., 2007).

Scrapie is a non-febrile, chronic disease of adult sheep and goats characterized clinically by pruritus, gait abnormalities, and a very long incubation period (1-7 years). It is also characterized by behavioral changes, including withdrawal from the flock, nervousness, and aggression toward inanimate objects (Kundul and Ame, 2022). Pregnancy toxemia is usually suspected in later pregnant ewes and shows nervous signs and a history of exertion, stress, or sudden deprivation of food. It is readily differentiated by the presence of ketonuria (Radostits et al., 2007).

2.9. Prognosis

Listeria infections lead to gastrointestinal disease or systemic syndromes both in humans and animals, thereby causing meningitis and subsequently grave prognosis. Complications due to *Listeria* infection include meningitis, sepsis, miscarriage, pneumonia, shock, abscess formation, stillbirth and inflammation of the eye. Mostly, humans recover from the gastrointestinal form of listeriosis but this form in animals may lead to meningitis. Overall case fatality rate is about 20%-30% in humans. Death rate of immunocompromised persons and newborn is usually higher (Janakiraman 2008).

2.10. Treatment

Listeriosis is treated with antibiotics; depending on the form of the disease, treatment may take up to six weeks or more. Due to some bacteria's intracellular location and disease occurrence in debilitated patients, the cure rate can be low (CDC, 2005). In the early stages of septicemic Listeriosis in ruminants respond to systemic therapy with ampicillin or amoxicillin. Recommended treatments include either oxytetracycline twice daily or penicillin-G (3 to 4 times per day for 7 days) (Wagner et al, 2005). Response to antibiotic therapy may be poor in neural Listeriosis although prolonged high doses of ampicillin or amoxicillin combined with an aminoglycoside may be effective (Barisani- et al.,2012). In animals, ocular Listeriosis requires treatment with antibiotics and corticosteroids injected sub conjunctively (Quinn and Markey, 2003).

The optimal antibiotic treatment for Listeriosis was penicillin, ampicillin, erythromycin rifampicin, chloramphenicol, tetracycline, and aminoglycosides, with the exception of cephalosporin are effective against *L. monocytogenes*. A combination of trimethoprim and tetracycline was more effective (Clark et al., 2004). Treatment involves administration of high doses of procaine penicillin every six hours for three to five days, then daily for an additional seven days. Forty-thousand IU per kg of body weight of procaine penicillin is needed to cross the blood-brain barrier and put sufficient amounts of the antibiotic into the tissue of the goat's central nervous system. Remember that one kilogram (kg) equals 2.2 pounds (Jolly 1999-2020). The standard treatment for CNS Listeriosis in adults is an Ampicillin 2 g IV every 4 hours with or without gentamicin for synergy. It is usually a disease of younger animals (under three years), as it is associated with tooth eruption and the emergence of the permanent molar teeth throughout the environment (Best treatment for Listeria in sheep 2020). For minor infections, medication might not be required (Healthline Media, 2004-2020).

The choice of treatment consists of a β -lactam antibiotic, normally Ampicillin. Because penicillin is bacteriostatic, some studies have attempted drug combinations. For example, the simultaneous use of Ampicillin and an aminoglycoside (usually gentamicin) is one of the most useful methods, especially in patients over age 50. The dose is important in the treatment of invasive disease, which requires a dose of 6 grams or higher (Lorber, 2010). In general, the length of antibiotic treatment increases with the severity of the infection. The treatment for meningitis lasts three weeks while brain abscess treatment lasts six weeks. The initial choice of antibiotics is usually IV ampicillin (Charles P.1996-2020).

2.11. Control and Prevention

Control is difficult because of the ubiquitous occurrence of the organism, the lack of a simple method of determining when it is present in high numbers in the environment and a poor understanding of the risk factors other than silage (Radostits et al.,2006). Control measures include reduction or elimination of feeding of silage, particularly poor-quality silage. All forms of stress should be minimized. Affected animals should be isolated and infected materials disposed of properly (Quinn, and Markey, 2003). Crucial factors for disease prevention include timely detection, keeping away/eliminating possible sources of infection, maintaining high hygiene/sanitation standards. Avoiding consumption of Listeria-contaminated foodstuffs prevents incidences of disease in human intracellular delivery of foreign antigens for the induction beings (Dhama et al., 2015).

Tetracyclines can be fed in the ration of animals at risk in a feedlot. When possible, the obviously spoiled areas of silage should be separated and not fed (Radostits et al., 2006). Sanitation of pens, water supply, pasture and housing should be improved (Fentahun and Fresebehat, 2012). In the case of abortion, isolate aborting does and ewes and send aborted fetuses and placentas to a diagnosis center for isolation of the causative agent. We have to wear latex gloves when handling placenta membranes. Vaccination with killed vaccines, which do not induce an effective cell-mediated response, is not protective because *L. monocytogenes* an intracellular pathogen. Live, attenuated vaccines, which are available in some countries, are reported to reduce the prevalence of Listeriosis in sheep (Quinn and Markey, 2003).

2.12. Public Health Significance

Listeria is an opportunistic intracellular pathogen that has become an important cause of human foodborne infections worldwide. Although *L. monocytogenes* is infective to all human population groups, it has a propensity to cause especially severe problems in pregnant women, neonates, the elderly, and immunosuppressed individuals and direct transmission is possible especially among veterinarians performing gynecological interventions with aborted animals. Animals may be diseased or asymptomatic carriers of *L. Monocytogenes* shedding the organism in their feces (Liu, 2006). Milk is supposed to constitute a complex ecosystem for various microorganisms including bacteria. Milk products like cheese, ice cream, and curd are widely consumed and the market for them has existed in many parts of the world for many generations. Raw milk and other dairy products are consumed by all age groups, including those populations at risk for contracting Listeriosis (Pal, et al. 2012a). The disease primarily affects older, pregnant women, newborns, and adults with weakened immune systems. However, rarely, persons without these risk factors can also be affected. Among the different species of the genus Listeria, *L. monocytogenes* has been known to cause Listeriosis in humans and animals (Shchukin et al., 2003; Pal, 2007).

Animals naturally harbor many food-borne bacteria in their intestines that can cause illness in humans, but often do not cause illness in animals. During slaughter, meat and poultry carcasses can become contaminated, if they are exposed to small amounts

of intestinal contents (Pal, 2015; Pal and Mahindra, 2015). Food safety has emerged as an important global issue with international trade and public health implications. *Listeria monocytogenes* associated with outbreaks have been reported in a wide variety of foods (Pal 2013; Pal and Awel 2014). The bacterium has been isolated from meat, poultry, milk, cheese, other dairy products, and vegetables (Antunes, et al. 2002; Kumar 2011; Khan, et al. 2013; Pal and Awel 2014; Pal 2015).

The Public Health Agency of Canada convened an expert panel in August 2008 to provide information to health care professionals and the general public on the diagnosis and management of Listeriosis during the recent outbreak. The following information is based on the panel's discussion and addresses what should be done for patients who have eaten food items that are suspected of being contaminated with *Listeria* and who have symptoms of diarrhea with or without fever. For healthy adults and children with a normal immune system, no *Listeria*-specific investigation is required. Gastroenteritis due to *Listeria* infection has a short duration and is self-limited in this population (Public Health Agency of Canada, 2006).

Healthy adults and children occasionally get infected with *L. monocytogenes*, but they rarely become seriously ill. The body's defense against *L. monocytogenes* is called "cell-mediated immunity" because it depends on our cells, especially lymphocytes called "T-cells." Therefore, individuals whose cell-mediated immunity is suppressed are more susceptible to the devastating effects of Listeriosis. Pregnant women naturally have a depressed cell-mediated immune system. In addition, the systems of fetuses and newborns are very immature and are extremely susceptible to these types of infections (Richard et al., 2008). any food-borne zoonoses are of serious public health concern with a long-term sequel to various organs. Among these, Listeriosis can cause severe and life-threatening complications. Owing to changes in food habits towards ready-to-eat products, food production systems, processing, and supply, refrigeration for food preservation, interest in organic and natural products, interest in free-range birds, and awareness towards better health, Listeriosis is now considered an emerging food-borne zoonosis of increased public health significance (Muñoz et al, 2012).

World Health Organization (WHO) defines zoonosis as those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man. There are approximately 1415 Pathogens known to affect humans of which about 61% of all human pathogens are zoonotic. Nearly half of all human infectious diseases known today can be classified as Emerging and about 75% of emerging infectious diseases are caused by zoonotic pathogens (Shchukin et al., 2003). The human population encounters animal diseases with varying frequency depending on their Occupation's geographical location and the prevailing culture of the country. Whether living in an urban or rural environment animal constantly may have close contact with a human on the farm (Food producing animals) at the area of residence (dogs, cats, cage birds) through leisure. Activities (horse, wildlife) or by virtue of the occupation of the individual as veterinarians or Animal nurses. This close contact can result in the occurrence and transmission of zoonotic Disease which is naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man (Erdogan 1998).

2.13. Status of Listeriosis in Ethiopia

Listeriosis is an emerging bacterial infection of human and animals, is typically caused by ingestion of *L. monocytogenes* through contaminated food and/or water (Pal, 2007; Derra et al., 2013). In another study (Firehiwot, 2007), 66 (27.4%) *Listeria* species were isolated from 240 food samples collected in Ethiopia and among these, 13 (5.4%) species were found to be *L. monocytogenes*. Another study has shown the presence and distribution of *L. monocytogenes* and other *Listeria* species in a variety of raw and ready-to-eat food products in Addis Ababa with a prevalence of 5.1%³⁴. Moreover, the prevalence rate of 4.1% was reported from raw meat and dairy products, such as raw milk, cottage cheese and cream cake collected from The Capital and Five Neighboring Towns in Ethiopia (Derra et al., 2013).

A recent study conducted at Gonder town public dining places shows that of 384 food samples examined, 96 (25.0%) samples were contaminated with *Listeria* species. *Listeria* species were isolated from raw minced beef, fish meat, pizza, raw milk, cottage cheese, cream cake, and ice cream samples (Gare dew et al., 2015). The findings revealed that the pooled prevalence of *Listeria* species in different food items of animal and plant origin in Ethiopia was 27%. The highest prevalence of *Listeria* species was reported in beef meat followed by ice cream with prevalence rates of 62% and 43%, respectively.

3.CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Listeriosis is one of the important food-borne bacterial zoonotic diseases worldwide, caused by *Listeria* spp. *Listeria monocytogenes* is most pathogenic for both humans and animals. *L. monocytogenes* has gained recognition as a global human pathogen because of the increasing incidence, diagnosis of infections and also, it is widespread in nature and lives naturally in plants and soil environments and has potential to introduce food plant. It can grow in a wide range of temperature and pH. Milk and milk products are important vehicles of *L. monocytogenes*, regularly causing Listeriosis outbreaks in different countries of the world. Carrier animals contaminate foods of animal origin such as meat and dairy products. There is a well-established linkage between silage feeding and Listeriosis. The complete elimination of *L. monocytogenes* on the farm level and from the food processing facilities, as indicated by the different researchers has been said to be difficult as *Listeria* species are ubiquitous to the environment. Good manufacturing and hygiene practices, particularly maintaining hygiene of processing machines, are the keys in preventing *L. monocytogenes* contamination. It is also equally important to notice that products, which may be subjected to post processing contamination, should be properly reheated before consumption by highly immune compromised persons in order to eliminate possible contamination. A food safety management system based on the principles of HACCP with

regular reviews should be developed and implemented in dairy plant. Based on the fact and information mentioned in the review the following recommendations are forwarded.

- ✓ Public health learning through Mass-media, radio and teaching livestock holder's and people who are at risk to *Listeria monocytogenes* is important.
- ✓ There should be proper disposal of aborted fetus and feces of infected animal to avoid spread of the disease.
- ✓ Consumption of unpasteurized milk and milk products should be avoided.
- ✓ Silage should be stored in the pH below 4.5 to maintain its quality.
- ✓ Susceptible animals should not be exposed to wet, cool and unhygienic environment

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